

The Containerisation of the ICON model for quasi-biennial oscillation simulations

Milestone MS2.4

1hr. QBO simulation (time step 40s., 20km resolution)

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Means of verifications: code test base, Docker container files, online documentation with performance results.

Achieved: Yes

Comments: *see milestone description below*

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Overview:

ETH/CSCS has the duty of providing stable computing resources for its customers' applications. In climate research this requirement often requires stable, reproducible execution of a particular application over multiple years. Since the underlying computing platform – in our case CSCS Piz Daint – changes with each upgrade, ensuring such continuity for users is at best challenging. ESIWACE2 is putting a large effort to evaluate containers to see if they provide the platform stability needed. The object of this milestone, *One model ported using containers*, is to illustrate first-hand the viability of the container paradigm.

The PRACE-supported QUBICC project which uses the Icosahedral Non-hydrostatic (ICON) model to simulate the evolution of the atmosphere in order to analyse the quasi-biennial oscillation (QBO) – the roughly 2-year shift from prevailing westerly mean flow to easterly and back – is one such application. The underlying high global resolution (2.9–5km) simulations require extensive computing resources over long periods of time, where the system needs to remain as static as possible. High performance is key to these simulations in order to complete them in reasonable time, so the overhead for running them inside a container has to be small.

While QUBICC simulations currently run on 'bare-metal', i.e., not within containers, ETH/CSCS and MPI-M are preparing the container infrastructure to support these simulations over the long term where machine upgrades are unavoidable. The ICON model was one of many models addressed in the [Container Hackathon for Modellers](#), a three-day event to 'jump start' the insertion of models into Docker-based containers. The results of this event are exhaustively documented in [ESIWACE-2 Deliverable D2.8](#). Of all the applications ported to containers during the hackathon, the ICON team arguably made the least progress. The work was subsequently continued by the ETH/CSCS User Support team: Rafael Samiento (ETH/CSCS) methodically extended the initial hackathon work and upgraded to the code base on the QUBICC branch `mc10_rrtmgp_remerge` from the `icon-cscs` repository.¹ The realisation can be found in a subsequent section.

The port of the ICON for QUBICC using containers was thus a *complete success* as illustrated by the performance comparison (see Appendix A.1) with the base code without containers, using a medium resolution simulation on 64 to 160 GPU nodes of Piz Daint: The overhead of running with containers turns out to be minimal. The resulting container infrastructure is highly useful for CSCS customers who need ICON to remain in a stable configuration for periods much longer than the normal upgrade cycle.

This milestone documents work contributing to Principle Objective (1) *Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021*. It enables the long simulations common in climate modelling on the rapidly changing environment of TIER0 supercomputers. By using Docker and Sarus, it makes use of the emerging container technology and thus contributes to the specific objective (b) *Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling*".

¹ This is a research version of the ICON software and is thus not a publicly available.

Realisation:

The containers employed are Docker-compatible, indeed a true Dockerfile is the end product of this work. However, Docker itself cannot be used on Piz Daint due to its need to have root access. Instead, the publicly available [Sarus framework](#), which is Docker-compatible, is used for the container execution. Sarus, however, does not have the facilities to build images; for this the publicly available [Buildah framework](#) is used.

The complicated software stack also requires a flexible software installation tool: for this the ICON development team has chosen the [Spack package manager](#), and this is also used in the container.

A Dockerfile was written to build ICON for QUBICC as well as to generate the example run scripts within a container. The Dockerfile is written in two stages: In the first, ICON and its dependencies are built/installed. This creates a temporary image into which, in the second stage, all necessary files and folders are copied. This is done to avoid having unnecessary files in the image and thus to keep its size as small as possible.

The `dockerfiles` and their documentation are in an ETH/CSCS-specific gitlab repository.² We subsequently refer only to the specific repository needed to construct the image, namely `dockerfiles/icon-cscs_mc10_rrtmgp_remerge`.

First stage: container to build the executable

The build Dockerfile expects:

- A cloned container repository, `dockerfiles/icon-cscs_mc10_rrtmgp_remerge`
- ICON sources
- PGI-19.10 compiler sources (downloadable from the Nvidia/PGI's web-site).

The Dockerfile expects the ICON source files saved compressed tar file named `icon-cscs_mc10_rrtmgp_remerge.tar.gz`, e.g., extracted from the icon-cscs repository, and the PGI sources as they are packed when downloaded from PGI's public-domain web-site: `pgilinux-2019-1910-x86-64.tar.gz`.

The image is then built using a SLURM batch script:

```
#!/bin/bash -l
#SBATCH --job-name=buildah-icon
#SBATCH --time=2:00:00 #SBATCH --nodes=1
#SBATCH --ntasks-per-core=1 #SBATCH --ntasks-per-node=1
#SBATCH --cpus-per-task=12 #SBATCH --constraint=gpu&contbuild
#SBATCH --hint=nomultithread
module load daint-gpu
```

² The container repository is currently under development, and is not public. It is ultimately intended for CSCS customers.

```
module load Buildah
cd $SCRATCH/dockerfiles/icon-cscs_mc10_rrtmgp_remerge
img_name='icon-cscs'
img_tag='mc10_rrtmgp_remerge'
buildah bud --tag ${img_name}:${img_tag}
buildah push ${img_name}:${img_tag} docker-archive:$SCRATCH/${img_name}-${img_tag}-buildah.tar
```

Here there are two main commands: `buildah bud ...` that builds the image and `buildah push ...` that saves the image as a tar file `icon-cscs-mc10_rrtmgp_remerge-buildah.tar` on `$SCRATCH`.

Second stage: running the container with Sarus

To run the container, the tar file with the image needs first to be loaded into Sarus:

```
sarus load icon-cscs-mc10_rrtmgp_remerge-buildah.tar icon-cscs:mc10_rrtmgp_remerge
```

This takes a couple of minutes. The loaded image can be listed with `sarus images`

REPOSITORY	TAG	DIGEST	CREATED	SIZE	SERVER
load/library/icon-cscs	mc10_rrtmgp_remerge	6abd38d042e6	2020-10-30	4.29GB	load

Sarus thus knows the image as `load/library/icon-cscs:mc10_rrtmgp_remerge`. Now it is possible to run ICON within the container. See Appendix A.1 for a medium resolution test example.

Building with Docker on a personal computer

Once again, Docker is not available on Piz Daint due to root access restrictions. But since normal Docker files are used, the image can alternatively be built with Docker on a laptop:

```
docker build -t icon-cscs:mc10_rrtmgp_remerge -f Dockerfile
```

As the images involved are quite large, this might take even longer than with Buildah mentioned above. The constructed image can be listed with `docker images`, similar to `sarus images` used previously. Once built, the image can be saved as tar file:

```
docker save icon-cscs:mc10_rrtmgp_remerge -o icon-cscs-mc10_rrtmgp_remerge.tar
```

The tar file can be copied to Piz Daint and loaded into Sarus exactly as it was done in the previous section.

Appendix A.1: Performance test for QUBICC 20km Global Run

In order to test the container concept without in expedient use of computing resources, we have chosen a 20km global resolution test case **hc11_01_pt1h_r02b07**, which fits on 64 nodes of the PRACE Tier-1 Piz Daint platform using Nvidia P100 GPUs. The test case is a one-hour simulation utilising full physics (turbulence, radiation, cloud microphysics, and other parameterisations) using a time step of 40 seconds. The strong scaling in the 64-160 node regime is not particularly good as the GPU's occupancy quickly decreases when more nodes are employed, but the goal here is not absolute scaling but rather the quantification of the overhead of using containers.

The run command entails some complexity in that file systems must be mounted in the container:

```
srun --mpi=pmi2 sarus run $pgi_mounts --mount=type=bind,source=/users,destination=/users \
--mount=type=bind,source=$SCRATCH,destination=/scratch/snx3000/sarafael \
--mount=type=bind,source=/scratch/snx3000/iconcontest,destination=/scratch/snx3000/iconcontest \
load/library/icon-cscs:mc10_rrtmgp_remerge-buildah \
bash -c "export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=/opt_ext/pgi/20.1.1/linux86-64-llvm/20.1/lib:/usr/lib:$LD_LIBRARY_PATH; cd
/scratch/snx3000/sarafael/icon-cscs/config/cscs/experiments/hc11_01_pt1h_r02b07; ${basedir}/bin/icon"
```

For completeness, this command is broken up into its components:

- `srun --mpi=pmi2` asks SLURM to enable `mpi2` support. We need this in order to use the MPI installation within the container instead of Piz Daint's native Cray-MPICH.
- `sarus run` is the Sarus command to run a given command within the container.
- `--mount=type=bind,source=/scratch/snx3000/iconcontest,destination=/scratch/snx3000/iconcontest` is an option passed to `sarus run` that's used to mount a Piz Daint directory on the container's file system. Here we are mounting Piz Daint's `/users/iconcontest/pool/data/ICON` at the same position within the container. ICON run scripts generated when building the image were set to expect the data there.
- `load/library/icon-cscs:mc10_rrtmgp_remerge-buildah` is the name of the image.
- The last part

```
bash -c "export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=/opt_ext/pgi/20.1.1/linux86-64-
llvm/20.1/lib:/usr/lib:$LD_LIBRARY_PATH; cd /scratch/snx3000/sarafael/icon-
cscs/config/cscs/experiments/hc11_01_pt1h_r02b07; ${basedir}/bin/icon"
```

is the command that runs the ICON simulation.

The table and figure below compare the timings of `hc11_01_pt1h_r02b07` without containers to runs within containers.

GPU Nodes:	64	96	128	160
Time w/o container	78.8 s.	55.2 s.	46.2 s.	38.4 s.
Time with container	83.0 s.	56.8 s.	47.3 s.	38.8 s.

Figure 1: Run times of an ICON simulation with and without containerization. There is only a minimal overhead due to the containerization, demonstrating the usefulness of this approach.

Appendix A.2: ICON QUBICC Dockerfile

The underlying docker file is highly specific to ICON and its build process, and in addition contains a number of sophisticated optimizations to minimize the size of the overall image. The intention here is not to explain its contents beyond the minimal in-lined comments, but rather to point out that the docker file will be maintained by CSCS on the long term for ICON users.

```
FROM nvidia/cuda:10.1-devel-ubuntu18.04
RUN apt-get update && \
    DEBIAN_FRONTEND=noninteractive \
    apt-get install --yes --no-install-recommends \
    wget \
    ssh \
    vim \
    ksh \
    less \
    environment-modules \
    tclsh \
    git \
    rsync \
    bison \
    flex \
    default-jdk \
    gfortran \
    curl \
    libcurl4-openssl-dev \
    libxml2-dev \
    python3.5 \
    ant \
    file \
    pkgconf \
    libssl-dev \
    cmake \
    nasm \
    python3-pip && \
    apt-get clean
```

```
RUN pip3 install --upgrade pip setuptools
```

```
RUN useradd -ms /bin/bash cscs
WORKDIR /home/cscs
```

```

USER cscs

COPY pgilinux-2019-1910-x86-64.tar.gz /home/cscs

# `apt-get install` puts libs and includes on different paths.
# Here we put libxml2's lib and include on the same place,
# otherwise ./configure can't find it.
RUN mkdir -p ~/.local/include ~/.local/lib && \
    ln -s /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/libxml2.a ~/.local/lib/ && \
    ln -s /usr/include/libxml2 ~/.local/include/

# Spack
ENV PATH=/home/cscs/spack/bin:$PATH
RUN git clone https://github.com/spack/spack.git
RUN cd spack && git checkout e916a9424ca6195e0685071f3bf3a8f532cb22fe

# Download PGI
# RUN wget -q -nc --no-check-certificate -O /home/cscs/pgilinux-2019-1910-x86-64.tar.gz --referer
https://www.pgroup.com/products/community.htm?utm_source=hpccm&utm_medium=wg&utm_campaign=CE&
nvid=nv-int-14-39155 -P /home/cscs https://www.pgroup.com/support/downloader.php?file=pgi-
community-linux-x64

# The following can be used to install PGI with spack.
# COPY pgilinux-2019-1910-x86-64.tar.gz /home/cscs
# COPY spack-pgi.py /home/cscs/spack/var/spack/repos/builtin/packages/pgi/package.py
# RUN spack install pgi@19.10

RUN tar -xvf pgilinux-2019-1910-x86-64.tar.gz
USER root
RUN cd install_components && \
    PGI_ACCEPT_EULA=accept \
    PGI_INSTALL_DIR=/opt/pgi \
    PGI_INSTALL_MPI=false \
    # PGI_INSTALL_NVIDIA=false \
    # PGI_MPI_GPU_SUPPORT=false \
    PGI_SILENT=true \
    ./install
USER cscs

# creates the entry for pgi@19.10 on ~/.spack/linux/compilers
RUN spack compilers && \
    spack compiler find /opt/pgi/linux86-64/19.10/bin

# the libpciaccess conflicts with pgi
RUN sed -i "s/depends_on('libpciaccess'/'# depends_on('libpciaccess'/'g"
/home/cscs/spack/var/spack/repos/builtin/packages/hwloc/package.py &&\
    sed -i "s/depends_on('libpciaccess'/'# depends_on('libpciaccess'/'g"
/home/cscs/spack/var/spack/repos/builtin/packages/mpich/package.py

# some packages need to be fixed
COPY spack.yaml /home/cscs/spack/spack.yaml
COPY netcdf-package.py /home/cscs/spack/var/spack/repos/builtin/packages/netcdf-
fortran/package.py
COPY claw-package.py /home/cscs/spack/var/spack/repos/builtin/packages/claw/package.py
COPY ivy-version.patch /home/cscs/spack/var/spack/repos/builtin/packages/claw/

# RUN bash -c '. /home/cscs/spack/share/spack/qa/setup.sh && spack install'
RUN bash -c '. /home/cscs/spack/share/spack/qa/setup.sh && spack install mpich@3.1.4%pgi@19.10'
RUN bash -c '. /home/cscs/spack/share/spack/qa/setup.sh && spack install jasper@2.0.14%pgi@19.10'
RUN bash -c '. /home/cscs/spack/share/spack/qa/setup.sh && spack install
eccodes@2.13.0%pgi@19.10'
RUN bash -c '. /home/cscs/spack/share/spack/qa/setup.sh && spack install libzip@2.1.1%pgi@19.10'
RUN bash -c '. /home/cscs/spack/share/spack/qa/setup.sh && spack install netcdf-
fortran@4.4.4%pgi@19.10'
RUN bash -c '. /home/cscs/spack/share/spack/qa/setup.sh && spack install claw@60d413%pgi@19.10'

COPY icon-cscs_mc10_rrtmgp_remerge.tar.gz /home/cscs

RUN tar -xvf icon-cscs_mc10_rrtmgp_remerge.tar.gz

RUN mkdir /home/cscs/icon/scripts/config_tests/docker-build

```

```
COPY docker-build/ /home/cscs/icon/scripts/config_tests/docker-build
```

```
ENV ICON_DOCKER=1
```

```
RUN bash -c '. spack/share/spack/ga/setup.sh && \  
  . /usr/share/modules/init/bash && \  
  module load mpich-3.1.4-pgi-19.10-4g7mk2b \  
             netcdf-fortran-4.4.4-pgi-19.10-zpancho \  
             hdf5-1.12.0-pgi-19.10-6f6hayd \  
             eccodes-2.13.0-pgi-19.10-3v6ct52 \  
             netcdf-c-4.7.3-pgi-19.10-k3oqqjj \  
             claw-d60d413-pgi-19.10-dtx4wow \  
             jasper-2.0.14-pgi-19.10-a3t5r6e && \  
  cd /home/cscs/icon/scripts/config_tests/docker-build && \  
  bash pgi.19.10.gpu && \  
  export use_site=docker && \  
  ./make_runscripts && \  
  make -j 4'
```

```
FROM nvidia/cuda:10.1-devel-ubuntu18.04
```

```
RUN apt-get update && \  
  DEBIAN_FRONTEND=noninteractive \  
  apt-get install --yes --no-install-recommends \  
  wget \  
  ssh \  
  vim \  
  ksh \  
  less \  
  environment-modules \  
  tclsh \  
  git \  
  rsync \  
  bison \  
  flex \  
  default-jdk \  
  gfortran \  
  curl \  
  libcurl4-openssl-dev \  
  libxml2-dev \  
  python3.5 \  
  ant \  
  file \  
  pkgconf \  
  libssl-dev \  
  cmake \  
  nasm \  
  python3-pip && \  
  apt-get clean
```

```
RUN pip3 install --upgrade pip setuptools
```

```
RUN useradd -ms /bin/bash cscs
```

```
WORKDIR /home/cscs
```

```
# Comment this to make the image smaller, /opt/pgi was copied
```

```
# to Piz Daint and I mount it on the container when running
```

```
COPY --from=0 /opt/pgi /opt/pgi
```

```
USER cscs
```

```
COPY --from=0 /home/cscs/spack /home/cscs/spack
```

```
COPY --from=0 /home/cscs/.spack /home/cscs/.spack
```

```
RUN mkdir -p /home/cscs/icon/scripts/config_tests/
```

```
COPY --from=0 /home/cscs/icon/scripts/config_tests/docker-build
```

```
/home/cscs/icon/scripts/config_tests/docker-build
```

```
COPY --from=0 /home/cscs/icon/externals /home/cscs/icon/externals
```

```
COPY --from=0 /home/cscs/icon/data /home/cscs/icon/data
```

```
RUN echo '. spack/share/spack/ga/setup.sh' >> /home/cscs/.bashrc && \  
  echo '. /usr/share/modules/init/bash' >> /home/cscs/.bashrc
```